

Computer simulation studies of nanoporous carbon-based electrochemical capacitors

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Among the various techniques that are used for understanding the operation of electrochemical energy storage devices, computer simulations are now playing a key role. In the case of electrochemical capacitors, the main driving force is the adsorption of ions at the surface of a nanoporous electrode, so that the most widespread simulation technique is molecular dynamics, which gives access to a microscopic picture. Here we review the most recent advances in the elucidation of charging mechanisms for a wide range of electrode geometries, ranging from slit to amorphous nanopores. We also discuss the impact of surface functionalization, doping and oxidation on the performance of electrochemical devices as predicted using such computer simulation techniques. Finally, we provide a few perspectives on the difficulties that still need to be overcome for fully understanding the complex systems which are used in electrochemical devices.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electrochemical capacitors are energy storage devices in which the charge is accumulated in the two electrodes through the adsorption of ions from an electrolyte at their surfaces. They are generally employed in applications for which Li-ion batteries power is not enough¹. After decades of optimization, the state-of-the-art devices now employ nanoporous carbons (with typical pore sizes smaller than 2 nanometers) for the electrodes and ionic species dissolved in organic solvents at relatively high concentrations for the electrolyte. Both the confinement and the ion concentration effects result in dramatic departures from conventional theories², so that over the years it was necessary to develop and combine a wide range of experiments, simulations and theories to fully understand the mechanisms at play during the operation of electrochemical capacitors³. Among the various approaches, computer simulation studies have played a pivotal role; in particular molecular dynamics has become the more widely used approach to obtain a realistic picture of the systems at the microscopic scale.

In this review we will therefore focus on the understanding provided by molecular dynamics simulations over the past few years. This method consists in determining the trajectory of a set of molecules over time; a typical instantaneous snapshot is shown on Figure 1. Newton's equation of motion is solved iteratively, in which the force is obtained by deriving an interaction potential. Structural and thermodynamic properties are then obtained by averaging over the full trajectory. Several approaches, with various levels of sophistication for the interaction potential, have been used for electrochemical capacitors. In short, the state-of-the-art consists in simulating the electrolyte molecules with all the atoms represented explicitly and the carbon electrode as a perfect metallic conductor held at constant potential. In order to reduce the computational cost, it is then possible to use coarse-grained models for the liquid and a fixed charge repartition for the electrode⁴. In the follow-

ing we will not discriminate between the various techniques unless specified. Although many studies have concerned planar electrode, we will focus on the case of nanoporous carbons since they are more relevant for technological applications.

II. SLIT PORES, CARBON NANOTUBES AND NANOPOROUS GRAPHENE

Most of the computational studies dealing with nanoporous electrodes involve slit-shaped pores or nanotubes. Although oversimplified with respect to realistic carbons, this allows i) to reduce the computational cost and ii) to simplify the analysis since the geometry of the system is defined by a unique parameter, i.e. the pore width or the radius of the tube depending on the geometry. In particular, the objective of the first studies was to understand the anomalous increase in the capacitance (i.e. the accumulated charge at a given potential) observed experimentally when the average pore size (as measured from gas adsorption studies) matches the ionic dimensions^{5,6}. By changing the radius of carbon nanotubes, a similar increase was also reported using simulations of ILs under confinement⁷. This study showed that the packing of ions of similar size was possible, an effect that was later explained by Kondrat and Kornyshev using a mean-field theory⁸. In this work, it was shown that the conductive walls induce an exponential screening of the electrostatic repulsion between the ions, leading to the formation of a "superionic state". In the case of slit pores, further works in which the pore width was systematically varied also revealed an increase of the capacitance when the pore size goes beyond another critical value, thus leading to an oscillatory behaviour of the capacitance⁹⁻¹¹.

However, it must be noted that all these simulations were carried out by considering a single slit pore (or nanotube), so that the influence of the double-side nature of the carbon walls is not considered. In order to account for

FIG. 1: Simulation cell of a 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate ionic and acetonitrile electrolyte mixture (simulated using a coarse-grained model) surrounded by disordered nanoporous carbon electrodes. Color scheme: blue, three-site 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium cations; red, single-site tetrafluoroborate anions; pale yellow, three-site acetonitrile molecules; silver, carbon electrode atoms. Gray molecules cap the cell in the z dimension, as this is nonperiodic. Reproduced from reference²⁵. Copyright 2016 American Chemical Society.

it, we have recently modeled a full supercapacitor made of IL and nanoporous graphene electrodes¹², with varying distances between the graphene sheets. We showed the existence of strong structural correlations between ions of the same charge belonging to different pores due to the image charges formed at the surface of the carbon, these correlations being much more remarkable in pores whose size is comparable to that of the ions and almost absent when the pores are wide enough to allow the formation of a bilayer of liquid inside them. In the disordered materials that are used for practical applications, it is expected that adjacent pores are separated by a monolayer of carbon as well^{13,14}, so that similar structural correlations may also occur.

Simulations of slit-pore shaped materials also allowed to understand the charging mechanism of supercapacitors and how it varies with the potential. For example, Bedrov and coworkers^{15,16} and Wu *et al.*¹⁷ showed that the nanopores are already wet by the electrolyte at the uncharged state. Then, the filling of the pores shows three different regimes: i) the swapping of co-ions in the pores with counter-ions in the bulk at low voltages, ii) the complete expulsion of co-ions from the pores and a densification of counter-ions when increasing the potential, and iii) a reduction of the capacitance at even higher electrode voltages due to pore saturation.

From the dynamic point of view, Kondrat *et al.* have studied the charging of nanoporous supercapacitors with ionic liquids¹⁸. They have shown that even though the over-filling of the narrow pores (due to an incoming flux of counter-ions that overweighs the outgoing flux of co-ions) occurs relatively quickly, the following de-filling is slowed down in a significant way. By simulating “ionophobic” pores, which are initially empty at null voltage, they observed a large acceleration of the dynamics, with an increase of the ions diffusion coefficients by one order of magnitude. Following this work, Breitsprecher *et al.*¹⁹ used two classes of models to compare the effect of finite and infinite long pores on the ion structure and charging. They observed that the pore entrance and closing

FIG. 2: Comparison of the capacitance of various electrode geometries as obtained from molecular dynamics simulation with a potential difference of 4 V between the electrodes. Reproduced from reference²⁰. Copyright 2013 American Chemical Society.

strongly influence the structure of ions inside the pores due to weaker image forces at the entrance and an additional closing surface that amplifies the image-force effects.

III. NANOPOROUS CARBONS WITH COMPLEX GEOMETRIES

Experimental nanostructured electrodes have a huge variety of shapes and dimensions that cannot be captured by slit pores electrodes. Changing the experimental conditions may lead to higher surface areas, diverse surface curvatures and varying atomic scale roughnesses. Importantly, they can have multiple kinds of confinements, which may lead to changes in the structure of the electrolytes and an enhancement of capacitive storage.

A systematic study of nanostructured carbon electrodes were performed by Vatamanu *et al.*, keeping a common ionic liquid electrolyte²⁰. They found that high curvature, atomic scale roughness and nanoconfinement structures are ideal electrodes with high capacitances as summarized on Figure 2. By analyzing the structure of the liquid, they observed that a larger curvature of the electrode allows to pack more counterions per surface area compared to a flat surface due to the effectively larger volume of the interfacial layer. The large local electrostatic fields generated at the atomically rough surface edges facilitate the ion segregation near the surface at lower voltages. Finally, they confirmed the results obtained in simpler geometries in the case of nanoconfinement, i.e. the presence of a significant screening of electrostatic interactions between ions, which can facilitate the separation of co-ions and counterions.

Based on the realistic structures of disordered nanoporous carbon electrodes obtained by Palmer *et al.*¹³, we were able to obtain quantitative comparisons with electrochemistry experiments. Our simulations showed that the larger capacitance of these systems is due to the formation of highly-charged carbon regions²¹. This local charge is linked to the degree of confinement of the liquid, and identified the presence of “hollow” and “pocket” sites that contribute strongly to the capacitance²². From the dynamic point of view, the diffusion coefficients of ions inside realistic nanoporous carbon structures are decreased by one order of magnitude with respect to the bulk at null voltage, and a further slowing down is observed upon application of a voltage²³. It is then possible to use an equivalent circuit model to determine the charging time of macroscale devices, for which we get typical times of a few seconds in agreement with the experimental data on similar systems²⁴. Finally, we have recently analyzed the impact of the ionic concentration in the liquid, by switching progressively from a pure ionic liquid to a conventional organic electrolyte²⁵. Our simulations, combined with cyclic voltammetry, showed that the capacitance of the device is not much affected due to an increasing difficulty of separating ions of opposite charges when they are more concentrated (while the presence of solvent screens the Coulombic interactions).

IV. DOPING AND FUNCTIONALIZATION OF THE CARBON SURFACE

Another important characteristic of carbon materials is that their density of state (DOS) may change very strongly from one material to another. This is particularly important for graphene-based electrochemical capacitors, because the low DOS at the Fermi level of this material restrict their performance. In order to improve the situation, nitrogen-doping of graphene electrodes has been proposed as an effective way to increase the capacitance. In order to assess this effect, molecular dynamics is not sufficient so that Hwang and coworkers²⁶

FIG. 3: Left: Comparison of the quantum capacitance C_Q for pristine and doped (N_1 and N_3V) graphene. The double-layer contribution to the capacitance C_D is given for an electrolyte composed of the 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate ionic liquid. Right: Representation of the electronic density of the two doped materials. Reproduced from reference²⁶. Copyright 2013 American Chemical Society.

have performed complementary density functional theory (DFT) calculations, that gives access to the quantum contribution to the capacitance (also called quantum capacitance). As shown on Figure 3, the latter is largely increased when switching from the pristine graphene material to doped systems, which confirms that doping is a promising strategy to obtain good performances.

Using oxidized graphene can also have a strong impact on the electrochemical response of the electrodes. De Young *et al.* investigated graphene oxide supercapacitors, where the electrode oxidation ranged from 0% (pure graphene) to 100% (fully oxidized) by decorating the graphene surface with hydroxyl groups²⁷. The capacitance tends to decrease with increasing electrode oxidation, which was attributed to a decrease in the reorganization ability of the electrolyte ions and the formation of a widening gap within the adsorbed layer. Xu *et al.* reported the same trend, i.e. a decreased capacitance in reduced graphene oxide supercapacitors when increasing of functional groups concentration. More recently, Dyatkin *et al.*²⁸ extended these works to the case of oxidized nanoporous carbons by adding -OH groups to the surface layers of slit pores. They showed that not only did the overall number of ions inside the oxidized pores become lower than in the pristine ones, but also that the diffusion coefficients were decreased by 1 – 2 orders of magnitude. These studies therefore show that the control of the oxidation state of the carbon structures is very important in practical applications.

Finally, a promising two dimensional metal carbide (MXene)-based electrochemical capacitor was investigated by Xu *et al.*, where the electrodes were allowed to move²⁹. The authors analyzed the ionic fluxes and the structural rearrangements inside the 2D material during charge and discharge processes. Different charge storage mechanisms were observed at the negative and the positive electrode, as shown in Figure 4: ionic exchange, intercalation and deintercalation occur concomitantly

FIG. 4: Analysis of the charging mechanism for two-dimensional $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes electrodes associated with a 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide ionic liquid electrolyte. The contributions of ionic exchange, intercalation and deintercalation are evaluated, and the arrows show the direction of swelling in the two electrodes upon application of a voltage. Reproduced from reference²⁹. Copyright 2018 Wiley.

with the swelling of the two electrodes.

V. CONCLUSION

In summary, molecular simulations have played a key role in the elucidation of the microscopic mechanisms at play inside carbon-based electrochemical capacitors. Note that we have discussed in this review only a fraction of the large variety of electrode geometries and electrolyte

compositions that have been studied, but in general most of the results show similar trends. However, it must be noted that the number of experimental setups which have been investigated is much larger, so that we believe a lot of work remains to be done. Among the main challenges that have to be overcome, the current electrode materials often involve complex electrode architectures, for which it will be necessary to obtain molecular models of good accuracy. In addition, the simulation of metallic electrodes is still in its infancy, and new interaction potentials accounting better for the electronic structure of the materials will have to be developed. Finally, the family of electrochemical capacitors is also extended to oxide-based pseudocapacitors, for which no models have up to now emerged in the literature. This will clearly be an intense field of research for molecular dynamics simulations over the next decade.

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